

Product relevant emotions in the Spanish language

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Abstract

This paper reports a five-stage study to identify what emotions are product relevant in Mexican culture, and to cross-compare these with the emotions identified in a prior study carried out in the Netherlands. 34 emotion terms in the Spanish language were identified as product relevant, 17 of which were related to product appearance. 21 emotion terms that were identified in this study coincide with the emotions reported in the Netherlands, especially with positive ones. Respondents reported more frequently positive emotion terms as product relevant than negative ones. This might have occurred because respondents had to recall the emotions that they experienced with products. Some of the emotion terms that were frequently elicited by product appearance in this study are: Atracción, Deseo, Diversión, Emoción y Sorpresa (Attraction, Desire, Amusement, Excitement, and Surprise). These emotion terms can be the basis for developing a rating scale for product emotions suitable for the Mexican context. We stress that more cultural studies are needed to have a better general validity of results, and to make the field of design research better at understanding emotions, emotional design and user experience.

Conference theme: Teaching across cultures design

Keywords: product relevant emotions, product appearance, design

Introduction

Research in the field of design and emotion is based on the findings of Psychology, a science that has a long tradition in the study of human emotions and their role in daily life.

Psychologists have determined that emotions affect human behaviour (Plutchik, 1980; Ekman, Friesen, & Ellsworth, 1982), social interaction (Fridlund, 1994), decision making (Isen, 1993), and motivation (DeCatanzaro, 1999). Furthermore, social psychologists have long noted the importance of cognitive appraisals in affective experience, with contextual and idiosyncratic factors significantly influencing self-reports of affective experience (Fridja, 1986; Lazarus, 1991). For example, cross-cultural studies regarding the emotion pride have converged on the finding that the experience of this emotion is culturally variant (Tracy & Robins, 2007; Scollon, Diener, Oishi, & Biswas-Diener, 2005). Russell (1989) and Wiles and Cornwell (1990) mention that emotions are strongly linked to culturally biased interpretation. One of the most radical differences lies in the labelling of feeling states, such as emotions (for an overview see Russell, 1991). Because labelling is an important aspect of conscious awareness of the feeling state, these linguistic differences should result in predictable cultural differences in the frequency and intensity of these emotions (Benet-Martínez & Oishi, 2008).

Product emotions

It has been well established that products elicit emotional responses in people (Fridja, 1986; Desmet, 2002; Norman 2004). Emotions are most relevant for product development because only they imply a one-to-one relationship between the affective state and a particular object (Frijda, 1986). Norman (2004) argues that products elicit emotions in three different levels: visceral, behavioural and reflective. Based on Norman's view, it is possible that a person experiences mixed emotions with the same product at one time, considering that at each level different emotions may be elicited.

Involved disciplines in product development started to study the role of emotions in products in different lines: studying the emotional response, or reaction to meaning, triggered by products in consumers (Jordan 1998; Desmet, 2002; Demirbilek & Sener 2003); proposing theoretical models on design and emotion (Desmet, 2008; Norman 2004); collecting information about consumer's emotional needs (Gaver, Dunne, & Pacenti, 1999; McDonagh, Bruseberg, & Haslam, 2002; Sperling, 2006). Within the emotional response triggered by products, attention has been paid to 'aesthetic emotions' (See Desmet 2003; Rafaeli & Vilnai-Yavetz, 2004). Scherer (2005) explains that 'aesthetic emotions' are produced by the appreciation of the intrinsic qualities of the beauty of nature, or the qualities of a work of art or an artistic

performance. Tan (2000) adds that ‘aesthetic emotions’ are a small group of emotions rather than the complete repertoire of human emotions. Cupchik (1999) pointed out that in contrast to artworks, industrial design objects are intended for practical use in everyday life and for mass consumption. The task-oriented approach, however, is changing, considering that consumers’ emotional needs were longer ignored (See Green & Jordan 2002; Hassenzahl & Tractinsky, 2006; Schniferstein & Hekkert 2008). Thus, it has been hypothesized that only specific emotions are relevant for the design, evaluation and marketing of products (Desmet, Hekkert, & Jacobs, 2000).

In a study carried out in the Netherlands for the Dutch language, Desmet (2002) identified 69 emotions elicited by products, of which 25 of these were often elicited by product appearance. Similar studies, however, have not been carried out in other countries. Considering that emotional responses are strongly influenced by culture and that some emotions are elicited by products, we report a five-stage study to identify what emotions are product relevant in the Mexican culture, and to cross-compare them with the emotions that were identified in the Netherlands. These two cultures differ in many cultural variables established by Hofstede (1991). Dutch culture is individualistic, low power distance, and feminine; Mexican culture is collectivistic, high power distance, and masculine. These differences should bring interesting insights in the field of product relevant emotions.

General characteristics of the study

In this study we focused on juvenile inhabitants of Mexico City (18 to 29 years old) with similarities in socioeconomic and educational levels. All respondents were native Spanish speakers. The ‘recollection method’ was used to assess consumer’s emotional response. It relies on consumers’ recollections of emotions elicited by products in daily life (Desmet, 2002). We focus on emotions evoked by seeing, touching, tasting, smelling or hearing a product, not those evoked by buying it in accordance with Desmet (2002) or the emotions that they could experience because the product was a special gift from a loved one. Thus, on the visual appearance of products that refers to all the product attributes that can be perceived from an image: colour, textures, materials, shapes, proportions, comfort, etc. (Ortíz, Takeda, & García, 2007). A significant aspect of this study was to trigger peoples’ memories regarding the elicited emotions they had experienced with products. For doing so, collages were created depicting a broad overview of durable products from the following categories: work, sports, household, travel and personal care. The ‘recollection method’ was used in phase 02, 04 and 05. In each of these phases, collages’ purpose was explained to respondents as: to trigger their’ memories

regarding experienced emotions with everyday objects. Moreover, different collages were used in each phase. Next section reports how the initial item pool was assembled.

Phase 01: Generating the initial item pool

Sanromán (2003) identified 135 terms for emotions in the Spanish language based on a semantic, syntactic and lexical analysis. She focused only on emotion terms in the Spanish language, which is why we consider her results in our study. Moreover, in Psychology, it is widely accepted to use words from daily life, dictionaries, etc. to study affective states (e.g. Allport & Odbert, 1936; Goldberg, 1981). Complementary to Sanromán's pool, a group of 69 product relevant emotions identified by Desmet (2002) were considered in our study based on: a) it is the only study in which a set of emotions was related to products, and b) this study had had a strong impact on industrial design research.

Desmet (2002) generated his initial pool using emotion terms in English that later were translated to Dutch. We selected the original English terms to translate them into the Spanish language, using the following process: two native Spanish speakers (a linguistic expert and a free-lance designer) with good knowledge of English translated independently the set of emotions. In a group session the results were discussed, and when disagreement occurred on the translated word, a native English speaker with a good knowledge of Spanish was consulted to choose the equivalent term in the Spanish language. When translation was finished, each emotion term was described with a noun to agree with Sanromán's pool (e.g. we use pride instead of proud). When this process was finished, 45 emotions from Desmet's pool were excluded from our 'initial pool' based on the following reasons:

- 38 emotions were already included in Sanromán's pool
- 2 emotions could not be transformed to nouns
- 5 emotions lost the original meaning

The 'initial pool' used in this study had 159 items (135 emotion terms from Sanromán and 24 from Desmet). In appendix A the initial pool is shown.

Phase 02: Experts' review

The assessment of the 'initial pool' was made by a group of experts in product development to identify product relevant emotions, as advised e.g. by Devellis (1991).

Participants

Ten respondents, four men and six women, participated in this phase. Three respondents had a background in Ergonomics and seven in Industrial Design (Three from academia and four from the professional field). The average age was 31.3 for the women and 30.5 for the men, with ages ranging from 26 to 38. These respondents were invited because they were recognized experts in their fields of work (respondents had an average of seven years of experience).

Material

An electronic questionnaire that consisted of two parts was developed. In the first part, three collages with a broad range of product images were included (See e.g. Figure 1). In the second part, the following sentence was posed: “daily life products make me feel...” Respondent then rated the 159 items based on three possible answers: “yes”, “no” or “I am not familiar with the emotion”. Five versions of the questionnaire were made with a different randomized emotions order each.

Figure 1: Some product images that were used to stimulate experts' memory

Procedure

Respondents were invited to participate in this phase by e-mail, which included a short brief about the aim of the study. It was mentioned that we were looking for professional experts in product development. If they agreed to participate, a second e-mail was sent including the written instruction and the electronic questionnaire. After they looked at the three collages, they filled out the questionnaire in one session within approximately 15 minutes.

Results

Based on the experts review, 34 emotion terms were eliminated from the 'initial pool'. 30 were evaluated as not experienced through products by any of the experts; 4 were unfamiliar by more than 3 experts. Generally, positive emotions were attributed to products more frequently than negative ones (e.g. pleasant surprise was chosen by 8 experts as product relevant whereas only 1 expert chose unpleasant surprise). On average 53.6 emotions for the women, and 31 emotions for the men, were attributed to be experienced through products, with responses covering a wide range of answers (19 to 66 emotions).

Phase 03: Psychologists review

This phase reports the assessment of 'pool B' by a group of psychologists to confirm that its items were emotion terms. It was done considering that most of the pool's items were semantically identified as emotions.

Participants

Five respondents, four men and one woman, participated in this phase. The average age was 39 years. Unpaid volunteers were recruited via the Centre of Experimental Psychology of the Faculty of Psychology of the National University of Mexico. This centre carries out studies in human emotions. The average professional experience of respondents dealing with human emotions was twelve years.

Material

A paper questionnaire was developed, containing 'pool B' with 125 items. Respondents rated each emotion based on two possible answers: "yes, it is an emotion" or "no, it is not an emotion". Five versions of the questionnaire were made, with a different randomized emotion terms order for each.

Procedure

The questionnaires were handed out to staff members of the Centre of Experimental Psychology. In the written instructions, a short brief about the aim of the study was given. It was stressed that we were looking for professional experts in the field of human emotions to assess

the items of 'pool B' based on their expertise. The test was completed individually in the working area of each expert.

Results

Based on experts review, 23 items from 'pool B' were eliminated. An item was eliminated when 80 % of the experts agreed that it was not an emotion term. 3 items that were not considered emotions by the experts were included in 'pool C', these are: boredom, pride, and inspiration. It was decided because these terms seem relevant for product development (e.g. it is interesting to identify if the appearance of a product is experienced as boring, inspiring, and so forth). For a further review see the discussion section.

Phase 04: Selecting product related emotions

This phase reports the assessment of 'pool C' by a group of consumers to identify what emotions are elicited by products.

Participants

Thirty respondents, 14 women and 16 men, participated in this phase. The average age was 22.2 years for the women, and 22.4 years for the men; ages covered a range of 18 to 29. Unpaid volunteers were recruited in four different points of Mexico City: Centre, South, North and West.

Material

A paper questionnaire was developed which included 'pool C' with 102 items. The following sentence was posed "daily life products cause me:..." Respondents rated each emotion based on two possible answers: "yes" or "no". Five versions of the questionnaire were made, with a different randomized emotion terms order for each. To stimulate respondents' memory three new collages were created and printed in A3 size pages (See figure 2).

Figure 2: A collage that depicts the range of products that were used in phase 4

Procedure

Respondents were approached in person and given a short brief about the aim of the study. When a person agreed to participate, written instructions were handed out. When instructions were read, each of the three collages was shown for 30 seconds. Later the questionnaire was handed out. Respondents filled it out in one session within approximately 10 minutes.

Results

Based on the respondents' reviews, 68 emotions were excluded from 'pool D'. Generally, respondents reported more positive emotions elicited by products than negative ones. Based on this phenomenon, three filters were established to determine what emotions are product relevant.

1. Emotion terms rated by more than 50% of respondents as elicited by products were included items of 'pool D'
2. Emotion terms rated by at least 45% of respondents and 50% of the experts in product development were included items of 'pool D' (E.g. 6 experts and 14 respondents rated admiration as elicited by products = 53% average)
3. For negative emotion terms a particular procedure was established: If the average sum of experts and consumers rating were equal to 25% or more, negative emotions were included items of 'pool D' (E.g. 5 experts and 13 respondents rated boredom as elicited by products = 46 % average)

On average 27.2 emotions were rated by women, and 22.8 emotions for the men, as elicited by products; responses covered a wide range of answers (7 to 59 emotions). Table 1 shows the 34 emotions that are elicited by products.

Admiration*	Eager*	Melancholy*	Illusion
Amazement*	Excitement*	Pleasant Surprise*	Strangeness
Amusement*	Fascination*	Satisfaction*	Surprise
Attraction*	Frustration*	Affection	Restlessness
Boredom*	Happiness*	Confidence	Nostalgia
Desire*	Hostility*	Esteem	Optimism
Disappointment*	Inspiration*	Contentment	Tenderness
Disillusionment*	Joy*	Displeasure	
Dissatisfaction*	Longing*	Fondness	

Table 1: Product relevant emotions (*Similar to Desmet's (2002) findings)

Phase 05: product appearance elicited emotions

This phase reports the assessment of 'pool D' by a group of respondents to identify what emotions are often elicited by product appearance.

Participants

A hundred respondents, 43 men and 57 women, participated in this phase. The average age was 22.5 for the women and 23.4 for the men; ages covered a range of 18 to 29. Unpaid volunteers were recruited in four different public universities of Mexico City, which are located in four different points: Centre, South, West, and East.

Material

A paper questionnaire was developed; it included 'Pool D' with 34 items. Three different qualities of each emotion were assessed:

- A) The degree in which the emotion is elicited by product appearance. A 5 point scale was used ('never' to 'always')
- B) Respondent's familiarity of each emotion. A 5 point scale was used ('unknown' to 'familiar')
- C) The valence assessment of each emotion. A 7 point scale was used ('negative' to 'positive')

Five versions of the questionnaire were made, with a different randomized emotion terms order for each. Four new collages were created to stimulate respondents' memory (See figure 3)

Figure 3: A collage that depicts the range of products that were used in phase 5

Procedure

A person of each of the involved universities was contacted and introduced to the study's purpose. Furthermore, it was requested to have a random group to carry out our quantitative study. The groups were briefed about the study's purpose and given oral instructions. It was stressed that the collages' purpose was to trigger their memories regarding product emotions. After the oral instructions, a power point presentation was shown with four slides that included the collages. Each slide was shown for 40 seconds to avoid fixation on stimuli. Later we handed out the questionnaire. Respondents filled it out in one session and within approximately 10 minutes.

Results

To investigate the differences between gender and emotional responses, a repeated measures MANOVA was performed with sex (2 levels) as the between-participant factor, and the 34 emotions as the dependents. No significant main effect of gender was found [$F(1, 16) = .36$, n.s.], indicating that the overall male emotional response did not differ from the female response. To investigate the product appearance relevancy, a T-test was performed for each emotion term. Figure 4 shows the mean score of each emotion based on appearance relevancy. The mean score overall of appearance relevancy ($Mo=2.74$) is indicated by a horizontal line. To exclude those emotions that are less relevant for product appearance we used the same method as a prior study (see Desmet 2002). The mean score of each emotion term was compared with the overall mean score to identify significant levels. In this study however the overall mean score is below the neutral mean score (3). We therefore considered a positive value as an overall mean score (3.1). A one-side t-test ($Df= 26$) was computed to identify significant levels. The t-test results indicated that the mean scores of 17 emotion terms were significant below Mo

($p < 0.01$). These emotions were excluded from the final set, reducing it to 17 emotion terms.

Table 2 shows the product appearance relevant emotions.

Attraction	Contentment	Joy*	Fascination*	Satisfaction*
Amazement*	Desire*	Illusion	Happiness	Surprise
Amusement*	Excitement	Inspiration*	Optimism	Pleasant surprise*
Confidence	Eager			

Table 2: Product appearance relevant emotions (*Similar to Desmet's (2002) findings)

Figure 4: Product appearance relevancy and familiarity of 34 emotion terms

The average score for each emotion term was computed for valence. It was determined that any emotion with a score of 4.68 or above on the valence scale was a positive emotion, while any emotion term with a score 3.32 or below was a negative emotion, and those emotion terms with an average falling between 3.33 and 4.67 were considered neutral emotions. These cut-off points were equal to those used by Whissell (1991). Table 3 shows the valence of the emotion terms used in this study.

Negative			Neutral			Positive		
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD		Mean	SD
Frustration	1.99	1.45	Nostalgia	3.47	1.77	Joy	6.19	1.18
Dissatisfaction	2.26	1.51	Longing	3.88	1.63	Happiness	6.07	1.19
Hostility	2.36	1.59	Strangeness	3.95	1.7	Optimism	6.04	1.14
Disappointment	2.52	1.58	Restlessness	4.15	1.82	Amusement	6.02	1.08
Disillusion	2.55	1.43				Satisfaction	6.02	1.18
Displeasure	2.84	1.54				Pleasant		
Boredom	2.63	1.53				Surprise	5.94	1.22
Melancholy	2.89	1.64				Contentment	5.91	1.23
						Confidence	5.81	1.43
						Fondness	5.81	1.43
						Eager	5.81	1.39
						Inspiration	5.75	1.35
						Affection	5.72	1.47
						Admiration	5.63	1.54
						Attraction	5.62	1.33
						Esteem	5.59	1.43
						Fascination	5.59	1.45
						Excitement	5.59	1.26
						Illusion	5.56	1.38
						Surprise	5.37	1.6
						Amazement	5.35	1.48
						Desire	5.15	1.65
						Tenderness	5.12	1.16

Table 3: Valence of product relevant emotion terms.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to identify what emotions are product relevant in Mexican culture. We identified 34 emotion terms that are product relevant; 17 of these are related to product visual appearance. 21 emotion terms coincide with Desmet's findings (2002) (See table 1). This is an interesting result considering that 135 items of our initial pool were Spanish terms. Moreover, Mexico and the Netherlands have strong cultural differences. It is important to point out that these similarities are with regard to emotion terms as such. The subjective experience of emotion, how each emotion is experienced, elicited, and so forth was not studied. Of equal importance, the back-translation criterion cannot be sufficient to claim exact emotion equivalency.

The results of this study also offer interesting insights. We identified twelve new product relevant emotion terms, these are: Esteem, Confidence, Fondness, Displeasure, Illusion, Strangeness, Surprise, Restlessness, Nostalgia, Optimism, Tenderness, and Contentment. In the general view, however, the emotion terms seem to share similarities among them e.g. happiness,

joy, and contentment; esteem, affection, and fondness; optimism and enthusiasm; surprise and pleasant surprise. For instance, in this study, no difference was found between pleasant surprise and surprise in terms of valence, familiarity and product relevancy. We included the term surprise as a result of this study because Desmet (2002) studied 'pleasant' and 'unpleasant' surprise. Surprise, however, was identified in both studies. Although we acknowledge that some emotions are similar among them, others offer new insights e.g. nostalgia. We can evoke nostalgia from e.g. a childhood toy or a retro product like the Volkswagen Beetle. Future research can study each term to identify the eliciting conditions or to discover the relationship between them.

Another similarity with Desmet's study was the positive emotion effect. Positive emotions were reported more often and with high scores in the last phase of both studies. Desmet (2002) reports that 13 of the 14 emotions with the highest mean scores were pleasant. In this study, 17 emotions with the highest score mean were also pleasant. This is particularly interesting because the respondents of the final phase from both studies differ in background. Desmet's respondents were specialists in product design. Our respondents were undergraduate students unrelated to any design or product development field. Respondents from both studies, however, were from academia. Desmet (2002) explains this effect, suggesting that when we experience unpleasant emotions with a product we simply ignore it. In addition to the latter idea, we discuss three issues that might have also influenced our results: a method effect, a user's experience effect, and a cultural effect.

Some psychological theories have suggested that there is a human bias to more readily perceived and process negative emotions (e.g. Pratto & John, 1991). Fredrickson (1998) mentions that negative emotions function to narrow a person's momentary thought-action repertoire. This function is without question adaptive in life-threatening situations that require quick and decisive action in order to survive. If no threat is perceived then it might be difficult to report negative emotions. Furthermore, Walker, Vogl, & Thompson (1994) have suggested that the unpleasantness of negative memories decreases at a greater rate than the pleasantness of positive memories. Similarly, Taylor (1991) mentions that although negative events have larger initial reactions, these reactions are often dampened more quickly and severely than reactions to positive or neutral events. Moreover, Ekman (1999) points out that most of what we know about subjective experience comes from questionnaires, filled out by people who are not having an emotion, trying to remember what it feels like. It is probable then that respondents have had difficulties in recall, and therefore report the unpleasant emotions they have experienced with products. Furthermore, presenting collages to the respondents might not be sufficient to trigger their memories.

In the field of user experience, Karapanos and colleagues (2008) suggest that in our first interactions with a product we may focus on its usability and the stimulation that it provides to us. After we use it for some time, we might become less concerned about its usability, and other aspects of the product, such as novel functionality or communication of a favourable identity to others, become more important (e.g. what the product expresses about its owner). Once the product expresses something about the owner, its reported qualities might be blended with the qualities of the owner (e.g. I am what I own). If we consider that we asked our respondents to report the emotions they experience with everyday products, respondents might have recalled their most appealing products; the ones that express something about themselves.

Culture might have also had an effect on our results. A recent study showed that people in Latin America value positive emotion and devalue negative emotion, even more than North Americans (Diener, Scollon, Oishi, Dzokoto, & Suh, 2000). Although the comparison is between Latin America (Including Mexico) and North America, the results indicate a cultural tendency towards positive emotions.

Based on the latter, we suggest that future studies use a set of physical products that people can see or even interact with (e.g. Desmet, Ortíz, & Schoormans, 2008). This will reduce any memory biases that may be associated with the recall method. Another important aspect is the heterogeneity of the product sample. Products must vary on as many features as possible: layout, colours, form, symbols, and signs as suggested by e.g. Hassenzahl (2004). Moreover, to reduce any biases associated with ownership, the product sample should exclude products that are owned by the respondents.

In phase 2 of this study we included three terms that were excluded by experts in human emotions. The inclusion of certain terms and the omission of others are however subject to intense debate in Psychology. Inspiration, for instance, has been said to be an appetitive motivational state (Thrash & Elliot, 2004), a personality trait (Allport & Odbert, 1936), an emotion (Davitz, 1969), and a cognitive condition (Clore, Ortony, and Foss, 1987). Similarly, boredom is experienced in different situations e.g. I am bored (Internal state), he is a boring person (personality trait), the product is boring (product quality). As mentioned in the introduction of this article, emotional design is based on Psychology findings, their end goals however differ. For designers it is more relevant to know how to create an inspiring product rather than the conditions of being inspired, which is a relevant topic for psychologists. Design research can then start by identifying the affective states elicited by products, which can be later studied to understand its eliciting conditions.

A limitation of the present research was that we focused on undergraduate samples from Mexico City, and future research should examine the generalizability of our findings to other populations within Mexico. It is also important to manipulate evocative stimuli in future research, as previously stated.

Conclusions

The topic of this article is relevant to the field of design and emotions, considering e.g. the assessment of emotion. Emotion terms play a central role in questionnaires and rating scales. We stress that additional cultural studies are needed to know if e.g. different cultures agree about the situations and contexts that elicit product emotions, to test the generalizability of theories, and so forth. Understanding how people experience emotions is relevant for similar follow-up studies or to establish new lines of research e.g. user experience does not limit itself to staring at a product, it includes a temporal relationship between the user and the product. Studying how this temporality affects the experienced emotions is also relevant. Cultural studies make us better at understanding emotions, user experience and so forth. With the knowledge gained from future studies, a better strategy could be established to deal with emotions, either in academia or professional design practice, which in our view is an attractive topic for the product experience research agenda.

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Appendix 1: Original pool

The Spanish emotion terms that were not identified as product relevant were translated into English using Gran Diccionario Oxford, Spanish to English, 2003.

Spanish	English	Spanish	English
Emotions that were eliminated during the 2nd phase:			
Abatimiento	Despondency	Inclinación	Inclination
Animadversión	Enmity	Inquina	Dislike
Arrepentimiento	Repentance	Ira	Anger
Bochorno	Embarrassment	Odio	Hate
Codicia	Greed*°	Ojeriza	Grudge
Cólera	Rage	Pasmo	Shock
Congoja	Distress	Pavor	Dread
Consideración	Consideration	Rabia	Anger
Desazón	Distress	Remordimiento	Remorse
Desdén	Disdain	Rencor	Rancour
Desengaño	Disappointment	Resentimiento	Resentment
Despecho	Rebound	Susto	Fright
Estupefacción	Stupefaction	Terror	Terror
Exasperación	Exasperation	Timidez	Shyness
Furia	Fury	Tirria	Grudge
Horror	Horror	Veneración	Veneration
Humillación	Humiliation	Vergüenza	Shame
Emotions that were eliminated during the 3rd phase:			
Adoración	Adoration	Desaprobación	Disapproval*°
Afición	Liking	Desconcierto	Bewilderment
Agradecimiento	Gratitude	Desconfianza	Distrust
Aislamiento	Isolation*°	Entretenimiento	Entertainment*°
Alivio	Relief	Estima	Esteem
Antipatía	Antipathy	Menosprecio	Contempt
Apego	Attachment	Pasividad	Passive*°°
Apetito	Appetite*°	Pesar	Sorrow
Avaricia	Avarice*°	Realización	Fulfillment*°
Cinismo	Cynic*°	Respeto	Deference
Concentración	Concentration*°	Simpatía	Sympathy
Curiosidad	Curiosity*°		
Emotions that were eliminated during the 4th phase:			
Aflicción	Affliction	Excitación	Arousal
Alarma	Alarm*°	Fastidio	Nuisance
Alborozo	Rejoicing	Furor	Furore
Amargura	Bitterness	Gozo	Enjoyment
Amistad	Friendship	Hastío	Tedium
Amor	Love	Indignación	Indignation
Angustia	Anguish	Infelicidad	Unhappiness
Aprensión	Apprehension	Irritación	Irritability
Asco	Disgust	Júbilo	Jubilation
Aversión	Aversion	Lástima	Pity

Calma	Calm*°	Mal Humor	Moodiness*°
Celos	Jealousy	Miedo	Fear
Chasco	Disappointment	Molestia	Irk
Compasión	Compassion	Nervios	Nervousness*°
Conmoción	Shock	Orgullo	Pride
Consuelo	Consolation	Pánico	Panic
Contrariedad	Setback	Pasión	Passion
Desconsuelo	Desolation	Pena	Sorrow
Descontento	Discontentment	Perplejidad	Perplexity
Desdicha	Misfortune	Perturbación	Disturb*°
Desencanto	Disenchantment	Pesadumbre	Grief
Desesperación	Desperation	Pesimismo	Pessimism
Desesperanza	Despair	Preocupación	Worry
Desolación	Desolation	Pudor	Decency/Shame
Desprecio	Contempt	Regocijo	Amusement
Devoción	Devotion	Relajamiento	Relaxation*°
Dicha	Happiness	Repugnancia	Repugnance
Disgusto	Disgruntlement	Repulsión	Repulsion
Encanto	Loving*°	Sentimiento	Feeling
Enemistad	Enmity	Sobresalto	Fright
		Sorpresa	Unpleasant surprise*°
Enfado	Annoyance	Desagradable	
Envidia	Envy	Temor	Fear
Esperanza	Hope	Tranquilidad	Compose*°
Euforia	Euphoria	Tristeza	Sadness

Product relevant emotions			
Aburrimiento	Boredom	Extrañeza	Strangeness
Admiración	Admiration	Frustración	Frustration
Afecto	Affection	Hostilidad	Hostility
Añoranza	Longing	Inquietud	Restlessness
Aprecio	Esteem	Insatisfacción	Dissatisfaction
Cariño	Fondness	Melancolía	Melancholy
Decepción	Disappointment	Nostalgia	Nostalgia
Desagrado	Displeasure	Ternura	Tenderness
Desilusión	Disillusion		
Product appearance relevant emotions			
Alegría	Joy	Ilusión	Illusion
Atracción	Attraction	Inspiración	Inspiration*°
Asombro	Amazement	Fascinación	Fascination*°
Confianza	Confidence	Felicidad	Happiness
Contento	Contentment	Optimismo	Optimism
Deseo	Desire	Satisfacción	Satisfaction
Diversión	Amusement*°	Sorpresa	Surprise
Emoción	Excitement	Sorpresa Agradable	Pleasant surprise*°
Entusiasmo	Eager		

*° 24 emotion terms included in the 'original pool' from Desmet's results (2002)